

Effectiveness of Live Selling Marketing Strategies as a Key Tool to Enhance Sales in the Fashion Business

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ABSTRACT: This research examines how live selling marketing strategies can boost sales for a fashion brand. Data was gathered through a questionnaire on the brand's Instagram, and Smart PLS was used for statistical analysis to understand the relationships between different factors. The results show that live selling significantly enhances customer engagement, sales conversion rates, and brand loyalty. The study confirms the reliability of the research model and highlights key factors that contribute to successful live selling, along with the challenges faced. Practical recommendations are provided to help optimize live selling strategies in the fashion industry. While the findings are specific to the selected brand, they offer valuable insights for other fashion brands looking to implement similar strategies.

KEYWORDS: Brand Loyalty, Consumer Behavior, Customer Engagement, Fashion Brand, Live selling, Smart PLS.

INTRODUCTION

The fashion industry is highly dynamic, influenced by changing trends, consumer preferences, and technology. One of the latest marketing strategies is live selling, where products are sold through digital platforms with direct interaction between the seller and buyer. Initially focused on fashion and beauty products, live selling now includes high-end furniture and luxury jewelry. This approach fosters social bonding, providing an in-store experience online. Live selling's two-way communication enhances consumer decision-making and effectively demonstrates product features, shifting viewers to active shoppers. Social networking sites like TikTok and Instagram, along with e-commerce platforms like Shopee, have popularized live shopping. This trend combines online shopping with real-time video streaming, boosting customer engagement and conversion rates.[1][2]. Understanding live selling is crucial for fashion retailers to stay competitive.[3][4]. Timothy Astandu, Co-Founder and CEO of Populix, notes that creative content and proactive interaction are key advantages of live shopping, enhancing purchasing power and community engagement. A survey of 506 people aged 17-45 in May 2023 revealed that 69% of respondents use Shopee Live most frequently, surpassing TikTok Live, Tokopedia Play, and LazLive. This research examines how live selling marketing strategies can boost sales for a fashion brand. Data was gathered through a questionnaire on the brand's Instagram, and Smart PLS was used for statistical analysis to understand the relationships between different factors. The results show that live selling significantly enhances customer engagement, sales conversion rates, and brand loyalty. The study confirms the reliability of the research model and highlights key factors that contribute to successful live selling, along with the challenges faced. Practical recommendations are provided to help optimize live selling strategies in the fashion industry. While the findings are specific to the selected brand, they offer valuable insights for other fashion brands looking to implement similar strategies.

1. How effective are live selling marketing strategies in enhancing sales for Fashion brand?
2. What are the challenges faced by Fashion brand in implementing live selling marketing strategies?

Despite the extensive research on live streaming in China (Xu et al., 2020), particularly in the e-commerce sector, there remains a significant gap in the literature concerning live streaming in Indonesia. The cultural, digital infrastructure, and consumer behavior differences between these two regions necessitate a focused study on Indonesia's unique context. While Chinese studies provide valuable insights, they may not fully capture the nuances of Indonesian consumers. This paper seeks to fill this gap by exploring how live streaming impacts consumer behavior in Indonesia's fashion industry. It aims to offer new perspectives on the role of live streaming in influencing purchasing decisions, building brand loyalty, and enhancing customer engagement in Indonesia. By addressing this gap, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on live streaming and provides practical insights for fashion brands operating in Indonesia. The paper begins with an introduction to the rise of live streaming in e-commerce. It reviews literature and applies the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework, focusing on factors like streamer

attractiveness and information quality. It then proposes a research model with hypotheses linking stimuli to consumer responses such as hedonic and impulsive consumption, mediated by cognitive and emotional states. The methodology section describes the study design, measurement development, and online survey data collection. Data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) tests the hypotheses, checking reliability and validity. The paper also investigates whether cognitive and emotional states mediate these effects, using bootstrapping. It concludes with a discussion of findings, implications, and recommendations for future research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Live Streaming Commerce

Direct sales marketing in the fashion industry, especially through live streaming, directly engages customers to boost sales and brand visibility. Unlike traditional e-commerce, live streaming allows real-time interaction between streamers (key opinion leaders) and viewers, providing dynamic product information and fostering virtual social relationships, enhancing the shopping experience and building trust [5]. This interactive environment integrates social activities and entertainment, driving sales through emotional connections [4]. Live streaming commerce creates para-social relationships, where viewers feel a sense of intimacy with streamers, enhancing trust and engagement. This interactive nature often evokes excitement, stimulating participation and impulsive purchasing decisions (Peng et al., 2024). These experiences are frequently shared on social networks, amplifying the social aspect of live streaming commerce [6].

2. Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) Framework Construct Identification

The Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework is essential for understanding consumer behavior [7]. It consists of three components: stimulus, organism, and response. Stimuli, whether external (website and marketing), internal (consumer traits), or situational (product options), trigger cognitive and emotional processes in individuals, leading to observable behaviors like purchases [8][9][8].

3. Stimuli in live streaming commerce

In investigating direct sales marketing strategies within the fashion business, influencers play a key role in creating engaging content. Using the S-O-R framework, we identify influencer attractiveness, para-social interactions, and information quality as stimuli that trigger viewers' emotional and cognitive responses. Influencer attractiveness involves perceived personality, appearance, and persuasive abilities [10]. Viewers may find traits like humor and diligence appealing, along with the influencer's appearance and convincing skills. Para-social interaction is the viewer's sense of personal connection with the live streamer [11]. This interaction is enhanced when streamers adjust their communication style and engage warmly with viewers' comments, fostering a virtual connection and perceived intimacy [12][7]. Live stream content, a contextual stimulus in the S-O-R framework, includes navigation, media format, and website features that drive engagement [13][14]. Information quality, crucial for engagement, refers to the usefulness, reliability, and completeness of the information presented. Real-time interaction allows immediate responses to inquiries and tailored product information, aiding consumer decision-making [10][15].

4. Organism in Live Streaming Commerce

In live streaming commerce within the fashion industry, the S-O-R paradigm suggests that environmental stimuli can alter individuals' internal states, both cognitively and emotionally [16]. Cognitive assimilation involves mental processes individuals undergo when engaging with such stimuli [7], such as assimilating product information presented online [9]. Viewers in live streaming commerce encounter cues like appealing streamers, interactive engagement, and information acquisition, which helps them evaluate recommendations and refine brand perceptions. Cognitive assimilation is defined as the modification of viewers' existing thoughts, beliefs, or attitudes through streamer influences [10]. Emotional reactions refer to the emotional responses individuals have when interacting with an environment [12]. These responses include intensity, arousal, excitement, and activation [9]. Arousal, ranging from sleepiness to frantic excitement, significantly influences motivation to engage in a consumption environment [8]. Approaching behaviors involve a desire to explore, engage, and find satisfaction in the shopping experience [6]. In this study, arousal is defined as how stimulated, active, or inspired a viewer feels by the streamer during the live stream [16]. Various stimuli, including attractive streamers, high-quality information, para-social interactions, and marketing strategies, cater to viewers' needs, entertain, and motivate participation in commercial activities

5. Responses in Live Streaming Commerce

Behavioral Brand Experience (BBE) refers to how direct interaction with a brand influences consumer behavior. In the context of live streaming commerce within the fashion industry, audiences are naturally drawn in, developing interest, absorbing product information, and recommendations with ease. They often find themselves captivated by the interactive experience, entertaining content, and the novelty of this shopping environment. This leads to diverse user experiences, fostering increased motivations for consumption and sharing behaviors. Viewers derive entertainment from the streamer's performance, perceive the shopping process as hedonic and engaging, and make impulsive purchases. They are eager to share their purchases and shopping experiences with friends, promoting the streamer within their social networks. Using the S-O-R framework, we identify impulsive consumption, hedonic consumption, and social sharing as key consumer behaviors in live streaming commerce. Impulse buying is a substantial part of retail turnover, characterized as an unplanned purchase made on the spot due to a stimulus [7]. E-commerce enhances impulse purchases by removing constraints found in physical stores [3]. In live streaming commerce, impulsive consumption includes pure impulse buying (enticed by novel products), reminder impulse buying (recalling prior experiences), suggestion impulse buying (influenced by comprehensive product information), and planned impulse buying (swayed by promotions and discounts). Social sharing involves viewers sharing their live streaming experiences on social networks, distinct from traditional online reviews. Live streaming platforms facilitate this behavior, allowing viewers to stream product information with commentary to their social networks. Social sharing includes sharing product review comments, streamers, streams, referrals, and recommendations across various platforms like WeChat, Facebook, and Microblog. This behavior is driven by utilitarian, emotional, and social benefits and has significant marketing implications for enhancing word-of-mouth, trendiness, and interaction [10].

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

- The Hypothesis would be Firstly Streamer Attractiveness: Attractive streamers enhance viewers' understanding and retention of information because they are more engaging and likable. H1a: Streamer attractiveness is positively associated with cognitive assimilation. Viewers experience heightened excitement and emotional arousal when interacting with attractive

streamers, making the live streaming experience more stimulating. H1b: Streamer attractiveness is positively associated with arousal. Second is Para-Social Interaction: When viewers feel a personal connection with streamers, they more effectively process and integrate information presented during the live stream. H2a: Para-social interaction is positively associated with cognitive assimilation. Strong para-social connections with streamers increase emotional excitement and engagement, leading to higher arousal levels. H2b: Para-social interaction is positively associated with arousal. After that the Information Quality: High-quality information provided during live streams helps viewers better understand and retain details about products. H3: Information quality positively influences cognitive assimilation. And then Cognitive Assimilation: When viewers effectively absorb information, they experience greater pleasure from their purchases, leading to more enjoyable shopping experiences. H4a: Cognitive assimilation positively influences hedonic consumption. Good cognitive assimilation encourages spontaneous buying decisions as viewers become more confident in the products they see. H4b: Cognitive assimilation positively influences impulsive consumption. When viewers understand and enjoy the products, they are more likely to share their positive experiences and recommendations with others. H4c: Cognitive assimilation positively influences social sharing. Lastly Arousal: Higher emotional excitement from live streams leads to increased enjoyment and pleasure in shopping. H5a: Arousal is positively associated with hedonic consumption. Elevated arousal levels make viewers more likely to make spontaneous purchases during live streams. H5b: Arousal is positively associated with impulsive consumption. Increased emotional excitement motivates viewers to share their experiences and recommendations with their social networks. H5c: Arousal is positively associated with social sharing.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a descriptive quantitative design to systematically analyze consumer behavior and brand loyalty for Triple Two Reworks. Data was collected from 132 respondents through a purposive sampling method using a questionnaire survey posted on the fashion brand's Instagram. The study was conducted on May 10, 2024. To encourage participation, 30 respondents who completed the questionnaire were randomly selected to receive a 30k E-Wallet reward. Data analysis includes descriptive statistics to summarize the findings and Structural Equation Modeling with Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) to examine relationships between variables. The measurement model is evaluated for validity, reliability, and goodness of fit. The structural model tests hypotheses using t-statistics and p-values to assess assumptions about brand loyalty and market success.

In this research, a quantitative approach is used to examine how brand loyalty can drive growth and enhance market success for the small clothing brand Triple Two Reworks. Data is collected through surveys from the target market and analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS) methods. The analysis begins with an external loading test to verify that indicators accurately measure the intended constructs. Construct reliability is assessed through Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha, with values exceeding 0.7 indicating good reliability. Convergent validity is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted (AVE), where values above 0.5 demonstrate strong indicator correlation. Discriminant validity is checked to ensure that indicators do not overlap between different constructs. To address multicollinearity issues, a collinearity test is conducted, and the model's explanatory power is assessed using R-Square analysis. Goodness-of-fit is measured by Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Through hypothesis testing, the research aims to identify significant relationships between variables, providing valuable insights into effectiveness of live selling marketing strategies as a key tool to enhance sales in the fashion business.

Construct	Item	Scales
Streamer Attractiveness	SA1	I think that the live stream streamer is talented.
	SA2	I think that the streamer has an enjoyable live streaming style.
	SA3	I think that the streamer has an interesting personality.
	SA4	I think the streamer has an appealing appearance.
Information Quality	IQ1	I think the content provided by the streamer is reliable (such as product, brand, and use experience).
	IQ2	In the live stream, I think the content provided by the streamer is true.
	IQ3	The streamer provides real-time information to meet my needs in the live stream.
	IQ4	In the live stream, I think the content provided by the streamer is complete.
Para-social Interaction	PS11	In the live stream, I feel as though the streamer and I are friends.
	PS12	When I am watching the live stream, I feel a sense of we-ness (togetherness) with the streamer.
	PS13	I feel as though the streamer cares about my responses during the live stream.
	PS14	I feel the streamer is like an old friend.
Cognitive Assimilation	CA1	While watching the live stream, my existing understanding regarding products/services is likely to be influenced through streamer information.
	CA2	While watching the live stream, my current knowledge regarding products/brands is likely to be influenced by streamers.
	CA3	While watching the live stream, my perceived value of the product can be transformed by streamer environmental cues.
	CA4	While watching the live stream, my preference of the product can be changed by streamer interaction.
Arousal	AR1	I feel enthusiastic about taking action while watching the live stream (e.g. shopping or social sharing).
	AR2	I feel exhilarated to participate during the live stream.
	AR3	I feel energized to initiate a variety of behaviours (suggestions/responses) during the live stream.
	AR4	I feel excited about engaging with the live stream.
Hedonic Consumption	HC1	The novelty of the live streaming shopping experience is pleasurable.
	HC2	The live streaming shopping entertains me.
	HC3	Being involved in the live streaming shopping is a fun experience.
	HC4	The live streaming shopping gives me a real high.
Impulsive Consumption	IC1	While watching the live stream, I buy things that I had not intended to purchase.
	IC2	While watching the live stream, I often buy things spontaneously.
	IC3	While watching the live stream, I often buy things without thinking.
	IC4	While watching the live stream, I feel like buying more things than I need.
Social Sharing	SS1	I pass information on brands, products, services and streamers from live streams to my friends.
	SS2	I share live stream information on my social networks.
	SS3	I share my own experience of the live stream, the streamer, and product on my social networks.
	SS4	I share live stream related posts on my social networks.

Figure 2. Questionnaire
Reference: Xu, Wu, dan Li (2020).

DISCUSSION

In this research, a quantitative approach is used to examine how brand loyalty can drive growth and enhance market success for the small clothing brand Triple Two Reworks. Data is collected through surveys from the target market and analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS) methods. The analysis begins with an external loading test to verify that indicators accurately measure the intended constructs. Construct reliability is assessed through Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha, with values exceeding 0.7 indicating good reliability. Convergent validity is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted (AVE), where values above 0.5 demonstrate strong indicator correlation. Discriminant validity is checked to ensure that indicators do not overlap between different constructs. To address multicollinearity issues, a collinearity test is conducted, and the model's explanatory power is assessed using R-Square analysis. Goodness-of-fit is measured by Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Through hypothesis testing, the research aims to identify significant relationships between variables, providing valuable insights into effectiveness of live selling marketing strategies as a key tool to enhance sales in the fashion business.

1. Reflective Model Measurement Result (Reflective Measurement)

a. Convergent Validity Test Result

Table 1. Testing Outer Loading

	S.A	IQ	PSI	C.A	AR	H.C	LC	SS
SA1	0.833							
SA2	0.926							
SA3	0.886							
IQ1		0.884						
IQ2		0.895						
IQ3		0.912						
IQ4		0.850						
PSI1			0.921					
PSI2			0.892					
PSI3			0.825					
PSI4			0.868					
CA1				0.813				
CA2				0.812				
CA3				0.858				
CA4				0.828				
AR1					0.855			
AR2					0.883			
AR3					0.912			
AR4					0.899			
HC1						0.776		
HC2						0.861		
HC3						0.920		
HC4						0.848		
IC1							0.809	
IC2							0.913	
IC3							0.899	
IC4							0.821	
SS1								0.821
SS2								0.925
SS3								0.911
SS4								0.905

The results of the outer loadings test in table 4.1 show that all indicators meet the loading factor value ≥ 0.70 . In addition, the AVE value must be > 0.50 to be considered adequate because if < 0.50 then more variance is caused by error variance than indicator variance.

Table 2. Testing Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)
S.A	0.779
IQ	0.784
PSI	0.769
C.A	0.686
AR	0.787
H.C	0.727
I.C	0.742
SS	0.794

Based on the AVE test results in Table 4.2, it can be seen that all indicators produce an AVE value > 0.50. So, it can be said that all indicators are considered to meet convergent validity and have a high level of validity.

b. Discriminant Validity Test Result

Table 3. Testing Cross Loading

	S.A	IQ	PSI	C.A	AR	H.C	I.C	SS
SA1	0.833	0.586	0.665	0.439	0.515	0.439	0.300	0.348
SA2	0.926	0.485	0.659	0.480	0.514	0.480	0.365	0.369
SA3	0.886	0.441	0.641	0.480	0.549	0.480	0.355	0.354
IQ1	0.524	0.884	0.524	0.492	0.490	0.437	0.346	0.241
IQ2	0.556	0.895	0.556	0.561	0.595	0.492	0.375	0.251
IQ3	0.562	0.912	0.562	0.490	0.586	0.561	0.436	0.300
IQ4	0.608	0.850	0.608	0.593	0.523	0.490	0.360	0.374
PSI1	0.921	0.616	0.921	0.536	0.617	0.593	0.337	0.434
PSI2	0.892	0.548	0.892	0.480	0.596	0.536	0.357	0.400
PSI3	0.825	0.600	0.825	0.576	0.614	0.480	0.243	0.267
PSI4	0.868	0.464	0.868	0.492	0.541	0.576	0.509	0.528
CA1	0.600	0.631	0.600	0.813	0.653	0.813	0.356	0.351
CA2	0.447	0.415	0.447	0.812	0.421	0.812	0.468	0.444
CA3	0.509	0.427	0.509	0.858	0.543	0.858	0.382	0.345
CA4	0.487	0.341	0.487	0.828	0.588	0.828	0.378	0.374
AR1	0.559	0.501	0.559	0.602	0.855	0.602	0.308	0.318
AR2	0.645	0.612	0.645	0.549	0.883	0.549	0.308	0.355
AR3	0.586	0.557	0.586	0.596	0.912	0.596	0.406	0.388
AR4	0.605	0.537	0.605	0.635	0.899	0.635	0.419	0.401
HC1	0.568	0.614	0.568	0.561	0.655	0.561	0.534	0.379
HC2	0.448	0.550	0.448	0.545	0.557	0.545	0.445	0.337
HC3	0.545	0.611	0.545	0.590	0.641	0.590	0.483	0.421
HC4	0.457	0.551	0.457	0.569	0.569	0.569	0.489	0.475
IC1	0.388	0.460	0.388	0.434	0.328	0.434	0.809	0.456
IC2	0.404	0.419	0.404	0.441	0.435	0.441	0.913	0.550
IC3	0.343	0.307	0.343	0.407	0.332	0.407	0.899	0.575
IC4	0.269	0.278	0.269	0.353	0.299	0.353	0.821	0.527
SS1	0.357	0.313	0.428	0.416	0.381	0.416	0.597	0.821

SS2	0.363	0.251	0.375	0.405	0.352	0.405	0.558	0.925
SS3	0.379	0.312	0.439	0.411	0.415	0.411	0.504	0.911
SS4	0.341	0.294	0.411	0.393	0.317	0.393	0.515	0.905

Based on the cross-loading test results, the questionnaire demonstrates good discriminant validity. Key findings include:

- SA - Streamer Attractiveness: The SA2 indicator (loading factor of 0.926) shows that streamers' attractiveness strongly influences participation in live selling.
- IQ - Information Quality: The IQ3 indicator (loading factor of 0.912) indicates that high-quality information impacts purchasing decisions.
- PSI - Para-Social Interaction: The PSI1 indicator (loading factor of 0.921) highlights the significant role of para- social interaction in increasing product interest.
- CA - Cognitive Assimilation: The CA3 indicator (loading factor of 0.858) suggests strong cognitive assimilation during live selling.
- AR - Arousal: The AR3 indicator (loading factor of 0.912) reflects high audience arousal, motivating purchases.
- HC - Hedonic Consumption: The HC3 indicator (loading factor of 0.611) indicates significant hedonic consumption impacts purchasing.
- IC - Impulsive Consumption: The IC2 indicator (loading factor of 0.913) shows a strong impulse to purchase.
- SS - Social Sharing: The SS2 indicator (loading factor of 0.925) suggests a strong desire to share experiences on social media, influencing purchases.

c. Reliability Test Result

Reliability testing on SmartPLS 3.0 consists of Cronbach's Alpha, R square coefficient, Composite Reliability (ρ_c), and AVE values. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the lower limit of construct reliability values to ensure composite reliability values with a value limit of > 0.70 . Meanwhile, Composite reliability (CR) is used to measure the actual value of construct reliability. CR is considered better when assessing the internal consistency of the construct with a value > 0.70 . The reliability test results in Table 4.4 show that the Cronbach's Alpha value is ≥ 0.70 , then seen from the Composite Reliability (ρ_c) value > 0.70 so it can be concluded that all dimensions are reliable.

Table 4. Testing Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability (ρ_a)	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)
S.A	0.857	0.859	0.913
IQ	0.908	0.914	0.936
PSI	0.899	0.902	0.930
C.A	0.848	0.854	0.897
AR	0.910	0.914	0.937
H.C	0.873	0.875	0.914
I.C	0.884	0.892	0.920
SS	0.913	0.914	0.939

2. Formative Measurement Model Result (Formative Measurement Model Result)

a. Outer Collinearity

Based on Table 5 below, all indicators in the outer collinearity test show VIF values below 5.00, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between indicators.

Table 5. Outer Collinearity

	VIF
SA1	1,826
SA2	3,194
SA3	2,528
IQ1	2,878
IQ2	3,101
IQ3	3,223
IQ4	2,295
PSI1	3,528
PSI2	2,916
PSI3	2,079
PSI4	2,606
CA1	1,645
CA2	1,824
CA3	2,305
CA4	2,109
AR1	2,386
AR2	2,640
AR3	3,416
AR4	3,020
HC1	1,627
HC2	2,653
HC3	3,601
HC4	2,341
IC1	1,960
IC2	3,632
IC3	4,035
IC4	2,431
SS1	1,905
SS2	4,087
SS3	3,579
SS4	3,705

b. Inner Collinearity : Based on table 6, all variables in the inner collinearity test show a VIF value below 5.00, only the variables CA, AR, and SS have a VIF value of 1.821. This shows that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between constructs in the SA, IQ, and PSI variables with VIF values of 2.308, 1.740, and 2.619 respectively. So it can be concluded that all independent variables in the model do not experience serious multicollinearity, because all VIF values are below the critical limit of 5.00.

Table 6. Inner Collinearity

	S.A	IQ	PSI	C.A	AR	H.C	LC	SS
S.A				2,308	2,308			
IQ				1,740	1,740			
PSI				2,619	2,619			
C.A						1,821	1,821	1,821

AR						1,821	1,821	1,821
H.C								
I.C								
SS								

3. Model Fit Testing Result (Goodness of Fit Model Result) : The Goodness of Fit model in SmartPLS is known as Model Fit which is obtained through bootstrap testing to evaluate model suitability. The model fit index can be seen from the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) and Normed Fit Index (NFI) values. Henseler et al. (2014, in Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2022) introduced SRMR as a suitability measure for PLS-SEM that is useful for avoiding model specification errors. The model is considered suitable if the SRMR value is less than 0.10 or 0.08.

Table 7. Goodness of Fit Model Testing

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.071	0.111

Based on the Goodness of Fit Model test results shown in Table 7, it can be concluded that the Saturated Model has an SRMR of 0.071, while the Estimated Model has an SRMR of 0.111. A lower SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) value indicates a better level of model fit to the observed data. In this case, the Saturated Model with an SRMR of 0.071 shows a good fit, because this value is below the generally accepted limit of 0.08. In contrast, the Estimated Model with an SRMR of 0.111 shows a poor fit, because its value is slightly higher than the accepted limit. This indicates that the Estimated Model may need improvement or modification to improve its fit to the data.

- 4. Direct Effect
 - a. F-Square and R-Square

Table 8. Testing F-Square

	F-Square	Results
S.A → AR	0.020	Low Effect
S.A → C.A	0.006	Low Effect
IQ → AR	0.109	Strong Effect
IQ → C.A	0.071	Low Effect
PSI → AR	0.114	Strong Effect
PSI → C.A	0.103	Strong Effect
C.A → H.C	0.148	Strong Effect
C.A → I.C	0.099	Low Effect
C.A → SS	0.076	Low Effect
AR → H.C	0.304	Strong Effect
AR → I.C	0.019	Low Effect
AR → SS	0.027	Low Effect

The F-Square test in Table 4.8 shows the results of the effect or influence between variables according to the research hypothesis as follows:

1. SA → AR, the F-Square value of 0.020 indicates that the influence of SA on AR is relatively low. This means that changes to SA only have a small effect on AR.
2. SA → CA, the F-Square value of 0.006 indicates that the influence of SA on CA is also relatively low. This means that changes to SA have very little effect on CA, almost negligible.
3. IQ → AR, the F-Square value of 0.109 indicates that the influence of IQ on AR is relatively strong. This suggests that changes in IQ have a significant effect on AR.

4. IQ → CA, the F-Square value of 0.071 indicates that the influence of IQ on CA is relatively low. This means that changes in IQ have a fairly small effect on CA.
5. PSI → AR, the F-Square value of 0.114 indicates that the influence of PSI on AR is relatively strong. This means that changes in PSI have a significant effect on AR.
6. PSI → CA, the F-Square value of 0.103 indicates that the influence of PSI on CA is relatively strong. This means that changes in PSI have a significant effect on CA.
7. CA → HC, the F-Square value of 0.148 indicates that the influence of CA on HC is relatively strong. This means that changes in CA have a significant effect on HC.
8. CA → IC, the F-Square value of 0.099 indicates that the influence of CA on IC is relatively low. This means that changes in CA have a fairly small effect on IC.
9. CA → SS, the F-Square value of 0.076 indicates that the influence of CA on SS is relatively low. This means that changes in CA have a fairly small effect on SS.
10. AR → HC, the F-Square value of 0.304 indicates that the influence of AR on HC is relatively strong. This means that changes in AR have a significant effect on HC.
11. AR → IC, the F-Square value of 0.019 indicates that the influence of AR on IC is relatively low. This means that changes in AR only have a very small effect on IC, almost negligible.
12. AR → SS, the F-Square value of 0.027 indicates that the influence of AR on SS is relatively low. This means that changes in AR have a fairly small effect on SS.

Table 9. Testing R-Square

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>R-Square Adjusted</i>
C.A	0.439	0.425
AR	0.528	0.517
H.C	0.573	0.566
I.C	0.242	0.230
SS	0.230	0.218

The R-Square test in Table 9 shows the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) to measure the extent to which the independent variable can explain variations in the dependent variable. Based on the test results, Cognitive Assimilation (CA) has an R-Square value of 0.439, indicating a weak influence. Arousal (AR) has an R-Square value of 0.528, indicating a moderate influence. Hedonic Consumption (HC) has an R-Square value of 0.573, also showing a moderate influence. Impulsive Consumption (IC) has an R-Square value of 0.242, indicating a very weak influence, and Social Sharing (SS) has an R-Square value of 0.230, also indicating a very weak influence. From these results, it can be concluded that the Arousal and Hedonic Consumption variables have a more significant influence in explaining variations in the dependent variable compared to the Cognitive Assimilation, Impulsive Consumption and Social Sharing variables which have a weaker influence.

b. Path Coefficient and P-Value Test

Path Coefficients testing on direct effects between constructs was carried out to assess the significance and strength of the relationship and to test hypotheses. The path coefficients value ranges from -1 to +1. The closer the value is to +1, the stronger the relationship between the two constructs. Conversely, a value close to -1 indicates that the relationship is negative. The hypothesis is accepted for direct effects if it shows T-Value > 1.96 and P-Value < 0.05 [18].

Figure 3. Model Output Path Coefficient and P-Value

Table 2. Testing Path Coefficient and P-Value

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Value	P Valuea
S.A → C.A	0.091	0.090	0.119	0.766	0.444
S.A → AR	0.148	0.144	0.107	1,381	0.168
IQ → C.A	0.263	0.251	0.104	2,526	0.012
IQ → AR	0.300	0.304	0.096	3,118	0.002
PSI → C.A	0.389	0.403	0.156	2,494	0.013
PSI → AR	0.375	0.378	0.108	3,469	0.001
C.A → H.C	0.339	0.340	0.081	4,160	0,000
C.A → I.C	0.370	0.384	0.118	3,132	0.002
C.A → SS	0.326	0.341	0.100	3,273	0.001
AR → H.C	0.486	0.489	0.094	5,192	0,000
AR → I.C	0.161	0.147	0.131	1,225	0.221
AR → SS	0.195	0.191	0.102	1,903	0.058

Based on Table 4.10, the testing of path coefficients and P-Values reveals the following insights:

- Streamer Attractiveness (SA) on Cognitive Assimilation (CA):** Not significant (T = 0.766, P = 0.444). Streamer attractiveness does not significantly impact viewer cognition.
- Streamer Attractiveness (SA) on Arousal (AR):** Not significant (T = 1.381, P = 0.168). Streamer attractiveness does not significantly influence viewer arousal levels.
- Information Quality (IQ) on Cognitive Assimilation (CA):** Significant (T = 2.526, P = 0.012). Higher information quality positively impacts audience cognition.
- Information Quality (IQ) on Arousal (AR):** Significant (T = 3.118, P = 0.002). Better information quality significantly increases audience arousal.
- Para-Social Interaction (PSI) on Cognitive Assimilation (CA):** Significant (T = 2.494, P = 0.013). Strong para- social interactions positively impact audience cognition.

6. **Para-Social Interaction (PSI) on Arousal (AR):** Significant ($T = 3.469$, $P = 0.001$). Good para-social interactions significantly enhance audience arousal.
7. **Cognitive Assimilation (CA) on Hedonic Consumption (HC):** Very significant ($T = 4.160$, $P = 0.000$). Improved cognition strongly influences hedonic consumption.
8. **Cognitive Assimilation (CA) on Impulsive Consumption (IC):** Significant ($T = 3.132$, $P = 0.002$). Better cognition increases impulsive consumption.
9. **Cognitive Assimilation (CA) on Social Sharing (SS):** Significant ($T = 3.273$, $P = 0.001$). Enhanced cognition positively impacts social sharing behavior.
10. **Arousal (AR) on Hedonic Consumption (HC):** Very significant ($T = 5.192$, $P = 0.000$). Higher arousal strongly drives hedonic consumption.
11. **Arousal (AR) on Impulsive Consumption (IC):** Not significant ($T = 1.225$, $P = 0.221$). Arousal does not significantly affect impulsive consumption.
12. **Arousal (AR) on Social Sharing (SS):** Not significant ($T = 1.903$, $P = 0.058$). Arousal does not significantly impact social sharing behavior.

To assess the effectiveness of live selling marketing strategies for the fashion brand, it's crucial to understand how Hedonic Consumption (HC) influences consumer behavior and purchase decisions. HC is about creating excitement and emotional engagement through products. For example, luxurious fabrics and attractive designs can lead to higher customer satisfaction and loyalty. While Cognitive Assimilation (CA) is important, it plays a secondary role compared to arousal. Consumers appreciate the brand's craftsmanship and details, but immediate emotional pleasure from the product's design is more impactful. Information Quality affects Arousal (AR), making clear and appealing communication essential. For the fashion brand, this means high-quality product descriptions, engaging social media content, and transparent information about the brand. Effective communication enhances emotional appeal and boosts HC. Parasocial Interaction (PSI) also plays a significant role, influencing both Arousal (AR) and Cognitive Assimilation (CA). Customers who feel a personal connection to the brand or its representatives are more engaged and likely to make impulsive purchases. By building a strong brand personality and fostering a loyal community, the fashion brand can leverage this connection. In the context of live selling, these factors are key to evaluating strategy effectiveness. Effective live selling should create emotional connections, provide clear and engaging information, and foster personal connections with the audience. These elements contribute to higher Hedonic Consumption, increased customer satisfaction, and greater brand loyalty, leading to sustained sales growth and a strong market presence. To assess the effectiveness of live selling marketing strategies for the fashion brand, it is crucial to understand the impact of factors like Hedonic Consumption (HC), Cognitive Assimilation (CA), Information Quality, and Parasocial Interaction (PSI). HC involves creating excitement and emotional engagement through products, which enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty. CA, while important, plays a secondary role to immediate emotional gratification provided by the product's design. Information Quality affects Arousal (AR) by highlighting the need for clear and appealing communication, which boosts emotional appeal and HC. PSI influences both AR and CA by fostering a personal connection with the brand, enhancing viewer engagement and trust. Challenges such as technical issues and maintaining viewer interest need to be addressed to optimize live selling strategies. Unstable internet connections and technical glitches can disrupt streams, impacting information absorption and engagement. Investing in reliable equipment and developing a diverse content calendar with interactive elements can help overcome these issues. By leveraging CA and PSI effectively, the fashion brand can enhance Impulsive Consumption (IC) and Social Sharing (SS), making live selling a powerful tool for reaching, engaging, and retaining its target audience.

CONCLUSION

Effectiveness of Live Selling Marketing Strategies: The implementation of live selling marketing strategies has proven to be effective for the fashion brand, significantly boosting sales and enhancing customer engagement. The empirical data collected from the questionnaire survey and the observed increase in sales figures before and after the introduction of routine live selling underscore the success of this approach. Live selling leverages influencer appeal, parasocial interaction, and high-quality information to create an engaging and emotionally resonant shopping experience. This method not only drives sales but also strengthens the brand's connection with its audience, highlighting the importance of integrating interactive and emotionally

engaging elements in marketing strategies.

Challenges and Solutions: Live selling has its challenges, such as technical issues and keeping viewers interested. Unstable internet can disrupt live streams and hurt customer satisfaction. To fix this, the fashion brand should invest in reliable streaming technology and a stable data plan. The fashion brand's host should remain interactive and create a lively atmosphere to keep viewers engaged. By focusing on these areas, the fashion brand can enhance the effectiveness of its live selling efforts and foster stronger consumer relationships. This study offers new insights into the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) theory by highlighting the importance of Hedonic Consumption (HC), Cognitive Assimilation (CA), Information Quality, and Parasocial Interaction (PSI) in live selling strategies within the fashion industry. However, there are limitations to consider. Firstly, the research may not fully capture the diverse consumer preferences across all of Indonesia due to sample constraints. Secondly, the role of PSI might differ in international markets or across other industries. For fashion industry practitioners in Indonesia, applying these insights can help design more effective marketing strategies by incorporating interactive and emotional elements in live selling. Emphasizing high-quality information and building strong personal connections can enhance customer engagement and brand loyalty. This practical application provides valuable guidance for addressing technical challenges and maintaining viewer interest in live streaming.

Future research should focus on several key areas. Expanding the sample size to include a broader and more diverse demographic, both within Indonesia and internationally, can offer a more comprehensive understanding of consumer preferences. Exploring the application of SOR theory in other industries, such as food, electronics, or services, can reveal whether these principles apply beyond fashion and how variables like PSI and HC translate across different contexts. Additionally, examining the impact of various live streaming platforms and technologies on strategy effectiveness can provide insights into optimizing live selling approaches. Longitudinal studies assessing the long-term effects of live selling on customer loyalty and sales outcomes, along with adapting strategies to evolving consumer trends, will further enhance the understanding of this marketing approach.

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